

Dynamic Multi-Sector Energy Economic Analysis to Identify Potential of Nuclear and Renewable Energy Options in Expanding Electricity Sector of Developing Countries: Bangladesh Case Study

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Abstract

Energy and electricity are very important for continuous growth and development, especially for fast-growing regions of the world. However, with the expansion of energy and electricity sector, the concern of environmental protection also arises. The cheaper electricity generation technologies from traditional fossil fuels involve huge emission of carbon which could easily jeopardize the global plan for climate action. In this study, we utilize the Dynamic Multi-Sector Energy Economic Model (DMSEE) to obtain long-term electricity sector expansion using traditional fuels and modern carbon-free nuclear and renewable energy options. The uniqueness of this model is the incorporation of economic interrelationships among top-down economic sectors and technological constraints of the bottom-up electricity sub-sectors simultaneously. To investigate the techno-economic shifts over time, we applied the model to one of the developing regions of the world, Bangladesh. The country is experiencing double digit growth in the electricity sector due to large-scale activities in the industry and service sectors. Carbon-emission limits of 25% and 50% with respect to projected growth have been considered to obtain potential scope of nuclear and renewable energy options considering technical and economic limitations simultaneously. The results of the analysis provide significant policy implications on the electricity generation mix under different circumstances.

Key words: Energy, Economy, Electricity, Carbon Emission, Bangladesh

1. Introduction

Developing countries experience increasing energy demand as they transform into industry based economy and people's purchase power increase. Most of the demand arises in the modern form like electricity¹⁾. The interrelation between economic growth and energy is important for national policy planning and sustainable growth, especially for the electricity sector.

Energy and economic growth could be linked through top-down (TD) energy models such as Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model. However, these models cannot elaborate the bottom-up (BU) electricity sector. In order to consider the technical characteristics of different electricity generation technologies, BU models are more appropriate such as Optimal Power Generation Mix (OPGM) model. Hybrid energy models are useful to interlink TD economic sectors with BU technical sectors for more detailed analysis and better understanding. In this study, we develop the hybrid energy model to analyze the optimum electricity sector development path for one of the fastest growing countries, Bangladesh. The results of the analysis are further discussed for policy implications.

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2. Overview of Energy and Electricity Sectors in Bangladesh

The primary energy source of Bangladesh is the indigenous natural gas, which contributes more than 50% of the present demand. As the country transforming from agriculture to more industry and commercial service oriented society, dependency on modern form of energy such as coal, oil and natural gas are increasing. Imported oil and petroleum products have a steady growth, mostly used in the transportation and power sector. Although there is a reserve of coal, a very small amount is used for primarily electricity generation. The overall contribution from the hydro (0.09 Mtoe), solar PV (0.03 Mtoe), wind and other renewable sources are too insignificant as shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1 Total primary energy supply (TPES) by source^{2, 3)}

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2.1. Natural Gas

Since first discovery in 1955 as of today 27 gas fields, 25 in the onshore and 2 in the offshore have been discovered in Bangladesh. Of them 20 gas fields are in production, one offshore gas field have been depleted after 14 years of production while other offshore field has not been viable for production due to small reserve. The estimated proven plus probable recoverable reserve was 28 Tcf (Trillion cubic feet). As of December 2020, a total of 18 Tcf gas has already been produced leaving only 10 Tcf recoverable reserve in proven plus probable category^{3, 4)}. The country has a daily production of 2,570 million cubic feet of natural gas and the current reserve of 10 Tcf would be exhausted by 2030 at current rate of production. To meet the growing energy demand of the country, the government initiated and started the import of LNG from august 2018. At present, a total of 1000 mmcf (Million Cubic Feet per Day) LNG is added to the national grid in order to support the growing demand. Natural gas production and LNG import from 2009-10 to 2019-20 financial year (July-June) is presented in **Fig.2**. The major consumers of natural gas in 2020 are also presented in **Fig. 3**. It is evident that the electricity sector (including captive power where Gas directly supplied to industries to produce electricity for own consumption and supply to the grid if available) consumes more than 60% of the total gas production including captive power for industries.

Fig. 2 Natural gas production trend in Bangladesh in Billion Cubic Feet (BCF) (2009-10 to 2019-20)³⁾

Fig. 3 Major consumers of Natural Gas in 2020³⁾

2.2. Coal

In Bangladesh, the reserve of coal (Bituminous Coal) is about 3 billion tones which is equivalent to 85 Tcf gas in 5 coal fields so far discovered. Out of the discovered mines, coal from 4 deposits (118-509 meters) is extractable at present. Production from Jamalganj may not be viable with present day's technology due to the depth of the deposits. Commercial production of Barapukuria Coal Mine commenced from 2005 using underground mining method with the targeted capacity of one million metric ton per year. Almost 65% of the production is being used by 250 MW coal fired power station near the coal mine. Coal might be the alternative fuel to natural gas that can conveniently meet the energy needs of Bangladesh for 50 years. The coal of Bangladesh is considered to be high quality due to high calorific value and low Sulphur content.

2.3. Oil and other fossil fuel resources

Petroleum products viz. diesel, petrol, octane furnace oil etc., account for about 22% of commercial energy supply in the country. Liquid fuel used in Bangladesh is mostly imported. Locally produced gas condensate shares only 6% of total liquid fuel consumption. Bangladesh imports about 1.36 million metric tons of crude oil along with 6.7 million metric tons (approx.) of refined petroleum products per annum. Major consumer of liquid fuel is transport followed by power, agriculture, industry and commercial sectors. Sector-wise consumption of petroleum products are: transport-50.26%, power-24.36%, agriculture 16.37%, industry 5.32%, domestic 3.21% and others 0.48%.

2.4. Potential of Renewable Energy

Renewable energy resources could assist in the energy security of Bangladesh and could help reduce the natural gas demand. Biomass is currently the largest renewable energy resource in use due to its extensive non-commercial use, mainly for cooking and heating in rural areas. It comprises almost a quarter of the total primary energy use in the country even though there is little potential of added resource due to high population density. There is only one conventional hydro-electric power plant in Kaptai, having 5 units with a total capacity of 230MW. Due to geographical limitations, large scale hydro is not a viable option in the country. Bangladesh is geographically located in a favorable position for harnessing sunlight, available abundantly for most of the year. Currently, the total solar PV installed capacity is near about 500MW, out of which only 150MW is connected to the grid. The rest are small-scale mostly roof-top and off-grid Solar Home Systems (SHS) established in remote and

rural areas. Some studies project that total installable solar PV capacity could reach 20~30 GW by 2041. Bangladesh is exploring the potential of wind power. In the coastal area of Bangladesh, windmills with a capacity of 2.9 MW are in operation. The wind speed at 80 meter altitude is good enough to harness wind power, especially in the coastal regions with an average capacity factor of 18%. However, the country still waits for a breakthrough in wind power technology to be competitive against other conventional commercial energy sources.

2.5. Electricity Sector in Bangladesh

Electricity is one of the modern forms of final energy due to ease in transmission and multiple applications. Recently, the country has observed more than 10% growth in the electricity sector over the last decade which might continue to grow at present rate of industrialization and increasing demand due to people's higher purchasing power. The electricity sector in Bangladesh is heavily dependent on the natural gas due to low cost and stable supply of the indigenous resource. Presently, it accounts for almost 70% of the electricity generated in the country. Gas-based combined cycle power plants serve the base load whereas some gas engines and mostly oil-based rental power plants serve the variable peak load.

Table 1: Installed Capacity and Electricity Generation Mix

Fuel	Installed Capacity (GW)	Generation Mix (TWh)
Gas	10.98	51.29
Oil	6.83	9.60
Coal	1.15	2.97
Import	1.16	6.67
Hydro	0.23	0.83
Solar	0.04	0.06
Total	20.38	71.42

Distributed rooftop solar home systems mostly serve the off-grid areas whereas some grid-connected mini-solar and experimental wind turbines are also contributing to the overall electricity mix. The country has a good potential of solar energy which has so far been utilized in off-grid areas as solar home systems. Now, the country is going for nuclear power and the construction of 2.4 GW nuclear power plant in Rooppur, Pabna is underway which is expected to start operation by 2024-25. In addition, electricity import from neighbor India is currently in action with present capacity of 1160 MW, with additional

potential interconnections currently under construction, while negotiations are going on with Nepal and Bhutan to import clean hydroelectricity through India. Bangladesh has limited potential for pumped storage due to geological position. However, battery storage is under strong consideration in order to utilize other variable renewables, especially solar PV. The present electricity installed capacity and generation for the 2019-20 financial year⁵⁾ are presented in **Table 1**.

3. Methodology

Energy modelling or energy system modelling is the process of building computer models of energy systems in order to analyze them. The models are used to project the future energy demand and supply scenarios of a country or a region⁶⁾. There are several methods of energy system modelling based on the specific purpose and input parameters used. From the analytical approach energy models can be categorized in two segments: Top-Down (TD) and Bottom-Up (BU) models. However, these models can have either descriptive or perspective outlook. BU models are generally focused on optimization and integrated assessment of the system. On the contrary, TD models combine the general equilibrium models and energy environment economy models. Hybrid energy models combine the top-down macroeconomic representation of a computable general equilibrium model with the bottom-up engineering details of energy production. Hybrid energy system models help understand the advantages and limitations of the existing BU and TD energy models and to improve the consultation process of the energy analysts for decision-makers⁷⁻¹⁰⁾. Some of the prominent hybrid models are NEMS, EMPIRE, GCAM, MARCAL-MACRO etc.

Dynamic Multi-Sector Energy Economic (DMSEE) model developed in this analysis, uses linear programming approach to quantitatively analyze the interrelationship among TD economic sectors and thus elaborate the BU electricity sector in term of different power generation technologies considering techno-economic and environmental constraints. We used the TD information obtained from Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) 10 database¹¹⁾ that represents the world economy through bilateral trade information. For the BU electricity sectors, seven power generation technologies were considered: coal-fired, gas-fired, oil-fired, nuclear, hydro, solar PV and wind power generation. Transmission and distribution sectors were also considered in the BU part including scope of power import from neighboring countries. The detail model formulation is further elaborated in subsequent subsections.

3.1 Top-Down CGE Modelling

DMSEE uses a linear approximation method to calculate nonlinear utility functions and production functions using linear programming for optimization. To consider substitution of goods, CES (Constant Elasticity of Substitution) type utility and production functions are considered. The general form of CES function is given by:

$$Y = \left(\sum_i b_i x_i^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} \right)^{\frac{\sigma}{\sigma-1}} \quad (1)$$

where, Y : production function or utility function, i : number of goods, b_i : input coefficient of good i , x_i : input quantity of good i , σ : elasticity of substitution.

As CES function is generally nonlinear and linear programming methods cannot be used to solve a programming problem having nonlinear constraints. Therefore, linearity is achieved by approximation of a linear function by the value of the substitute elasticity as shown below.

$$Y = \min\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i, \dots\} \quad \text{if } \sigma \rightarrow 0 \text{ (Leontief type)} \quad (2)$$

$$Y = \left(\prod_i x_i^{b_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{\sum_i b_i}} \quad \text{if } \sigma \rightarrow 1 \text{ (Cobb-Douglas type)} \quad (3)$$

$$Y = \sum_i b_i x_i \quad \text{if } \sigma \rightarrow \infty \text{ (Linear type)} \quad (4)$$

Following linear approximation is adopted to incorporate it in the linear DMSEE model. Assuming $\rho = (\sigma-1)/\sigma$ and number of goods i in eqn. (1):

$$Y = \left(\sum_{i=1}^I b_i x_i^\rho \right)^{\frac{1}{\rho}} \quad (5)$$

Now, the price, P_i of the good i is obtained by partially differentiating the production function with respect to the quantity x_i as:

$$P_i = \frac{\partial Y}{\partial x_i} = Y^{1-\rho} b_i x_i^{\rho-1} \quad (6)$$

Then, assuming the cost c in this production is to be minimized, we have

$$\text{minimize } c = \sum_{i=1}^I x_i \cdot P_i, \text{ s.t. } (5) \quad (7)$$

Now, using envelop theorem and considering the Lagrangian \mathcal{L} in eqn. (7) we get

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial x_i} = -\rho \cdot \lambda \cdot b_i \cdot x_i^{\rho-1} = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow x_i^\rho = \left(\frac{P_i}{\rho \cdot \lambda \cdot b_i} \right)^{\frac{\rho}{\rho-1}} \quad (9)$$

Here, the Lagrange multiplier λ is an undetermined constant. Substituting this in the cost eqn. (7) and obtaining the undetermined constant λ we get

$$c = Y \left(\sum_{i=1}^I b_i \left(\frac{P_i}{b_i} \right)^{\frac{\rho}{\rho-1}} \right)^{\frac{\rho}{\rho-1}} \quad (10)$$

From Shepard's lemma, since the price partial derivative of cost is equal to the variable quantity, the input coefficient β_i of x_i and are obtained as:

$$x_i = Y \left(\frac{P_i}{b_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{\rho-1}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^I b_i \left(\frac{P_i}{b_i} \right)^{\frac{\rho}{\rho-1}} \right)^{\frac{1}{\rho}} \quad (11)$$

$$\beta_i = \left(\frac{P_i}{b_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{\rho-1}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^I b_i \left(\frac{P_i}{b_i} \right)^{\frac{\rho}{\rho-1}} \right)^{\frac{1}{\rho}} \quad (12)$$

The price is determined by the shadow price of the inequality $x_i \geq \beta_i \cdot Y$. A nonlinear type production process can be considered by linearly approximating to the Leontief type. To find b_i we multiply both sides of eqn. (6) by x_i and apply summation to get:

$$Y = \sum_{i=1}^I x_i \cdot P_i \quad (13)$$

Substituting this to eqn. (6) we get variable quantity and price:

$$b_i = P_i \left(\frac{x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^I x_i \cdot P_i} \right)^{1-\rho} \quad (14)$$

From the above analysis, the input coefficient β_i is fully given only by the variable quantity and price and that is the solution of the CGE model. Therefore, by repeating the calculation and updating the variable quantity and price, the production value of the original CES type production function can be improved. Furthermore, in order to improve the accuracy of the approximation, this model performs repeated iterations to calculate the input coefficient and production function of multiple points using the convex hull approximation. That means, if the input coefficient obtained at the time a is β_i^a , then

$$\sum_a \beta_i^a \cdot y^a \leq x_i \quad (15)$$

$$\text{s.t. } Y = \sum_a y^a \quad (16)$$

If it is considered in a two-dimensional plane, a convex curve is composed of multiple straight lines, and if it is considered in a three-dimensional space, a convex cone is composed of multiple straight lines. This is equivalent to convex hull approximation in each plane. As a result, $a = 1$, that is, the price information by iterative calculation. This allows a more reproducible approximation of the original curve than without updating.

3.2 Objective Function

The overall objective function of the model is to maximize utility function for the household and government consumptions. The utility loss due to taxes is deducted from the utility at each time point. The present value is calculated at a discount rate and maximizing the added objective functions in all regions and at all-time points is considered.

maximize:

$$obj = \sum_{r \in RR} \sum_{y=0}^{Y-1} \sigma_{r,y} \left(\left(util_{H,r,y} + util_{G,r,y} \right) - \left(tax_{T,r,y} + tax_{B,r,y} \right) \right) \quad (17)$$

where, $util_H$ and $util_G$ are the utilities obtained through household and government consumptions as explained in equation (1).

$$\text{subject to } \sigma_{r,y} = \left(\sum_{t=0}^{y-1} e^{-\tau \cdot \text{DiscountRate}_r \cdot t} \right) e^{-\tau \cdot \text{DiscountRate}_r \cdot y} \quad (18)$$

where, r : regions of analysis (Bangladesh in this case), y : analysis years, H : household, G : government, T : top-down sectors, and B : bottom-up sectors, $util$: utility.

3.3 Constraints for Optimization

The following constraints have been adopted as per ¹²⁾ for the analysis region for all time points unless otherwise specified:

(a) Supply-Demand Balance: Goods produced by activities are consumed by households and government; so demand cannot exceed the supply of that good.

$$h_B + g_B + a_B + i_B = c_B \quad (19)$$

$$h_T + g_T + a_T + i_T = c_T \quad (20)$$

where, h : household consumption, g : government consumption, a : intermediate consumption, i : investment, p : production, k : capital of equipment, l : labor, m : import, x : export, B : BU and T : TD sectors. Intermediate input matrix of TD and BU consumptions consumed by TD and BU activities could be related with investment matrices as shown in eqn. (21-24).

$$a_B = A_{BT} \cdot p_T + A_{BB} \cdot p_B \quad (21)$$

$$a_T = A_{TT} \cdot p_T + A_{TB} \cdot p_B \quad (22)$$

$$i_B = C_{BT} \cdot p_T + C_{BB} \cdot p_B \quad (23)$$

$$i_T = C_{TT} \cdot p_T + C_{TB} \cdot p_B \quad (24)$$

(b) Physical/Resource Balance: The bottom up goods produced are divided into domestic consumption and export. Therefore,

$$\sum_{n \in BAR} E_{B_{m,n}} \cdot xp_{B_{m,r,y}} = xd_{B_{m,r,y}} + xt_{B_{m,r,s,y}} \quad (25)$$

$$(m \in BCR, s \in RR2, r \neq s)$$

$$xc_{B_{m,r,y}} = xd_{B_{m,r,y}} + xt_{B_{m,r,s,y}} \quad (26)$$

where, xp : domestic production, xd : domestic consumption, xt : export/import, xc : total consumption, $E=1$ if there is production, 0 otherwise for n : activity and m : goods. Since the physical balance of the TD sectors takes into account substitutability, it is given by the formulation of CES function linear approximation. The physical reserve of fossil fuel resources used in this analysis is presented in **Table 2** for Bangladesh and whole world.

Table 2: Physical reserve of fossil fuel

Fuel	(unit)	Global ¹³⁾	Bangladesh ^{2,3)}
Coal	Giga-ton coal eq.	747	0.293
Oil	Giga-ton Oil eq.	243	0.004
Gas	Trillion cubic meter	199	0.186

(c) Capital Investment: Each activity increases the depreciation of equipment by investment and enhances the production capacity. So, production is restricted by installed capacity in BU sectors.

$$k_{B_t} = k_{B_0} + \sum_{t=0}^t F_{B_{i,t}} \eta_{i,t} i_{B_t} \quad (27)$$

where, k_B : installed capacity, F : investment matrix, η : construction cost

(d) Labor and Production: Production requires labor as well as equipment. The labor force is measured in terms of population growth efficiency factors. The labor force at a particular time is related with the previous time point as shown in eqn. (28).

$$l_{t+1} = (1 + \zeta) e_t \cdot (1 + \theta) l_t' \approx (1 + \zeta + \theta) l_t = (1 + \gamma) l_t \quad (28)$$

where, l : labor force, l' : number of labors, e : efficiency of labor, θ : population growth rate, ζ : technology progress rate, $\gamma = \theta + \zeta$.

Assuming a stationary equilibrium state of the solution, eqn. (29) is derived from the relationship between investment and capital stock and eqn. (27). Therefore, theoretical value of γ could be calculated by considering the ratio of rental payment to investment.

$$(\gamma + \delta) V_{n,0} = i_{n,0} \quad (29)$$

The number of labor population between the ages of 15-64 of Bangladesh has been adopted from UN population projection ¹⁴⁾ as shown in **Fig. 4**.

Fig. 4 Labor population projection (2020-2100)

(e) CES function linear inequality approximation: DMSEE has introduced a production function for the production of goods in the TD sector in order to consider the substitutability of goods. The Armington hypothesis is also introduced considering the substitutability of domestic goods and imported goods. Since all of these production functions are CES- type production functions and are generally nonlinear functions, to consider as linear programming problems, it is necessary to approximate linearly. If the utility or production function be z , the variables of CES function be y , the coefficients of Shephard's lemma be β , then the approximation of primary inequality could be expressed as:

$$\beta_{i,j,t} \cdot z_t \leq y_{i,j,t} \quad (30)$$

The model is solved repeatedly and β is updated with the solutions and the shadow prices of the previous calculation until it reaches saturation.

3.4 Bottom-up sectors Incorporation

The BU sectors for this analysis includes power generation technologies (both fossil and renewable technologies) and transmission and distribution systems. The base year information is required for the model development and future new construction and technical parameters are listed in **Table 3 – 5**. Each generation technology has different technical and environmental limitations in addition to system restrictions. Major characteristics and limitations of the BU electricity subsectors are also explained with formulations.

Table 3: Assumptions for Thermal Power Generation

	Nuclear	Coal	Oil	Gas
Initial capacity [GW]	0.0	1.25	6.75	11
Construction cost [\$ /kW]	3500	1500	1200	1000
Annual Average Availability [%]	80	78	80	83
Seasonal Peak Availability [%]	85	90	95	90
Maximum Increase Rate of Output [1/h]	0.02	0.26	0.44	0.44
Minimum Increase Rate of Output [1/h]	0.02	0.31	0.31	0.31
Life Time [year]	50	40	30	40
Share of Daily Start and Stop	0.8	0.3	0.3	0.3

Table 4: Assumptions for Renewable Power Generation

	Hydro	Solar PV	Wind	Biomass
Initial capacity [GW]	0.25	0.5	0.01	0.01
Construction cost [\$ /kW]	2400	900	1500	3000
Annual Average Availability [%]	65	-	-	70
Maximum Increase Rate of Output [1/h]	0.05	-	-	0.05

	Hydro	Solar PV	Wind	Biomass
Minimum Increase Rate of Output [1/h]	0.05	-	-	0.05
Life Time [year]	60	25	30	40

Table 5: Assumptions for Battery Storage Facilities

	Battery
Initial capacity [GW]	0
Construction cost [\$ /kW]	-
Construction cost [\$ /kWh]	600
C-Rate	0.14C
Self-discharge Rate [%/hour]	0.05
Availability Factor [%]	90
Efficiency [%]	85
Life Time [year]	15

BU Constraints for optimization are:

(i) Electricity demand and supply balances: the total power generation from all generation technologies and storage medium should equal to the power demand at each hourly time step. It is given by:

$$Load_{y,d,t} = \sum_i P_{y,d,t,i} + (Pdis_{y,d,t} - Pcha_{y,d,t}) \quad (31)$$

(ii) Operational constraints: The output of various renewable power generation technologies are mostly dependent on seasonal, geographical and daily variations. Accordingly, capacity factors along with hourly availability of the generation technologies are defined based on historical data. For the fluctuating renewable sources, output suppression is allowed to discard the excess electricity if it seems to be cheaper than adding more storage technologies. For solar and wind-power generations, the upper limit was set by using the capacity factor every hour, and output suppression could be implemented as in eqn. 32. For hydropower, the daily maximum operational limit was set as it depends on natural conditions.

$$\eta \cdot p_{B_{n,t}} \leq C_{u_{n,t}} \cdot k_{B_n} \quad (n \in \{solar, wind, hydro\}) \quad (32)$$

(iii) Capacity reserve constraints: To maintain electricity supply reliability, reserve capacity (10% in this case) is assured as per eqn. (33). The power supply of hydro, wind and PV is not considered in the capacity reserve due to its unpredictable output profile, although the certain ratio of PV output is reported to be expected.

$$\sum_{i=2}^6 A_{y,d,i} \geq (1 + \delta) \times Load_{y,d,t} \quad (33)$$

(iv) Maintenance constraints: Nuclear and other thermal power plants shut down their facilities at an appropriate time of year for maintenance. In this study, the maintenance pattern of each day was expressed by superimposing the seasonal maintenance pattern set for every season. The corresponding equations are:

$$ap_{pl,d} + \sum_{m=0}^3 Ur_{m,d} mk_{m,d} = k_{B_{pl}} \quad (34)$$

$$\sum_{m=0}^3 Ur_{m,d} mk_{m,d} \geq (1 - Up_{pl}) k_{B_{pl}} \quad (35)$$

$$\sum_{m=0}^3 \sum_{d=0}^{364} \frac{Ur_{m,d} mk_{m,d}}{365} = (1 - Ua_{pl}) k_{B_{pl}} \quad (36)$$

where, $Ur_{m,d}$: rate at which the plant shuts down on day d in the repair seasonal pattern m , $ap_{pl,d}$: operation capacity at day d of plant $pl \in \{NuclearE, coalE, oilE, gasE\}$, $mk_{m,pl}$: Capacity at which plant pl stops according to repair seasonal pattern m , Up_{pl} : maximum daily operation rate of plant pl , Ua_{pl} : average annual operation rate of plant pl .

As the amount of power generation is limited to the operating capacity $ap_{pl,d}$, eqn. (37) need to be satisfied.

$$\eta \cdot P_{B_{pl,d,t}} \leq ap_{pl,d} \quad (37)$$

(v) Load following capability: Some power plant has its own load following capability, whereas some cannot change its output abruptly. Hydro and gas-fired power plants can slowly change its output level, which account for the load following properties. Considering the upper and lower limits of the load following operation as $MaxLF$ and $MinLF$ eqn. (38, 39) needs to be satisfied.

$$P_{B_{pl,t}} \leq (1 + MaxLF_{pl}) P_{B_{pl,t-1}} \quad (38)$$

$$P_{B_{pl,t}} \geq (1 - MinLF_{pl}) P_{B_{pl,t-1}} \quad (39)$$

(vi) Reserve Capacity: The spinning reserve capacity of the system has been considered as 5% of the total maximum demand, $MaxLOAD$ as expressed in eqn. (40).

$$\sum_{pl} k_{B_{pl}} \geq (1 + 0.05) \cdot \eta \cdot MaxLOAD \quad (40)$$

(vii) Charge and discharge balance of storage technology: eqn. (41) explains the balance of power charge and discharge for stored electricity in a storage facility and formulated to illustrate the state of stored energy for batteries, which is governed by self-discharge rate and their round-trip storage efficiency. Charge cycle efficiency and discharge cycle efficiency of the battery are equal to the square root of the round-trip efficiency. The flexibility of charge and discharge is characterized by C-rate for a rechargeable battery such as NAS and Li-ion battery as illustrated in eqn. (42) and eqn. (43).

$$SE_{y,d,t,j} = SE_{y,d,t-1,j} \times (1 - SDL_j) + (Pcha_{y,d,t-1,j} \times \sqrt{Eff_j} - Pdis_{y,d,t-1,j} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{Eff_j}}) \times H \quad (41)$$

$$EC_{y,j} \leq C_{y,j} \times MDC_j \quad (42)$$

$$C_{y,j} \leq EC_{y,j} \times CRT_j \quad (43)$$

The interrelationship between the TD and BU sectors and the flow of the DMSEE model is summarized in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Incorporation of TD and BU sectors in Dynamic Multi-Sector Energy Economic (DMSEE) Model

4. Input and Scenario Development

The base year input data for domestic consumption, import, and export for the analysis region Bangladesh was obtained from GTAP 10 database that provides a snapshots of the global economy for reference year 2014. For each country/region, the Data Base presents values of production, and intermediate and final consumption of commodities and services in millions of U.S. dollars obtained from country-based Input Output Tables. For the BU energy and electricity sectors, the sources of base year data include several national reports and publications¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Based on the per-capita annual consumption growth rate, three different scenarios were developed naming (a) business as usual (BAU) growth: 7%, (b) low growth (LG): 6% and (c) high growth (HG): 8%. In order to observe the effect of carbon emission constrains, two CO₂ emission reduction scenarios starting from 2025 and reaching (a) 25% (Quarter) and (b) 50% (Half) by the year 2050 with respect to BAU emission were considered. The results from different scenarios provide implications of different socio-economic and energy policy scenarios on the energy and electricity-mix in addition to providing linkage with the overall economic sectors.

5. Results Analysis

The dynamic model obtained the optimal power generation mix at 5 years interval starting from 2020 and ending at 2050. It also computes the production, consumption, import and export including intermediate consumption among different economic

sectors to get the real picture of the economic growth. The GDP for LG, BAU and HG scenarios are presented in Fig. 6 (a), (b) and (c) respectively.

Fig. 6 (a) GDP and Composition at Low Growth (LG) Scenario

Fig. 6 (b) GDP and Composition at BAU Growth Scenario

Fig. 6 (c) GDP and Composition at High Growth (HG) Scenario

As energy consumption is directly linked with economic activities, the growth of electricity sector also follows the trend which can be observed in Fig. 7 (a), (b) and (c) where changes in electricity mix has been shown for different growth scenarios.

It has been observed that mostly fossil fuel-based energy sources are selected as a result of optimization as no carbon emission constraint was imposed. There is hardly any contribution from imported oil. However, the newly introduced nuclear energy seems to have a good prospect in all different cases for Bangladesh. As the consumption growth increases, natural gas fails to play an important role due to depletion of existing reserve. However, domestic and imported coal supports the base load generation due to cheaper fuel cost both from local and imported cases. Significant coal contribution is also observed at the later

time points due to higher demand in greater consumption scenario. Solar power share reaches its maximum potential even though the contribution in the generation mix is not that significant due to low capacity factor and lack of sufficient available land area in the highly dense region. Wind power generation from the coastal regions appear in the generation mix from 2050, which also has limited potential due to low-capacity factor at average height.

Fig. 7 (a) Electricity generation-mix at Low Growth Scenario

Fig. 7 (b) Electricity generation-mix at BAU Scenario

Fig. 7 (c) Electricity generation-mix at High Growth Scenario

Per capita CO₂ emission in Bangladesh (0.5 ton in 2019) is well below world average (4.4 ton in 2019)¹⁸. In order to assess the impact of carbon-restriction on the energy mix, 25% and 50% reduction with respect to the BAU case until 2050 are considered which are in line with the government's commitment to UNFCCC as per Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDC)^{19, 20}. The electricity mix in BAU growth scenario (per-capita annual 7% consumption growth) with CO₂ emission restrictions is presented in Fig. 8 (a) and (b). The effect on economy due to emission reduction constraints for the year 2050 are presented in Table 6.

Fig. 8 (a) Generation-mix at 25% CO₂ Emission Reduction

Fig. 8 (b) Generation-mix at 50% CO₂ Emission Reduction

Table 6: Effect on CO₂ Emission Restrictions in 2050

	BAU (no emission reduction)	25% CO ₂ emission reduction	50% CO ₂ emission reduction
CO ₂ emission (Mt)	410	307.8	204.6
GDP (Billion \$)	3071.03	2977.53	2884.04
GDP Loss (%)	-	3.04	6.09
Loss in Industry Sector (%)		4.21	7.84
Loss in Service Sector (%)		3.02	5.92
Loss in Agriculture Sector (%)		1.86	3.78
Energy Demand Reduction (%)		1.29	2.56
Electricity Demand Loss (%)		2.84	5.48

Imposing CO₂ emission limits have negative effects on the overall GDP, energy and electricity demand. However, the effect on electricity demand is less than that on GDP and more than that on energy in both the cases. Previously, in the BAU case, fossil fuel contributed more than 37% of the generation mix of 2050. In the restricted scenarios, contribution from coal and gas comes down to 31% and 27% respectively. It is observable that by introducing emission restriction policy renewable energies appear in the energy mix and the contribution from renewables (solar PV and wind) becomes more than 13% of the total generation in 2050. Nuclear power bears the major share for emission reduction by contributing nearly 60% of the total load by 2050. Even though there is some increase in the imported electricity during the middle part of the analysis duration. But it does not continue for

long due to high cost of import. Development of infrastructure i.e. transmission lines for the import of electricity is observed as it plays the role of backup reserve.

In order to achieve climate change goals to limit global mean temperature rise, such option to introduce nuclear and renewables might be essential even for developing countries. However, imposing carbon restriction is reflected mostly by large-scale deployment of nuclear power to reduce share of coal. Contribution from solar PV is fully utilized (30 GW installed capacity in 2050), which is limited due to insufficient land area. Also, contribution from wind power is low due to low capacity factor and higher cost of construction at high altitudes with natural disaster risks such as cyclones.

6. Conclusion

Developing countries like Bangladesh are switching to modern and cleaner energy options like nuclear and renewables in order to satisfy their growing need while maintaining energy security and keeping the carbon emissions within limit. However, the consequence of new energy technologies on the overall economy is quite significant and that needs to be analyzed in advance considering the interrelationship among different economic sub-sectors.

In this analysis, a hybrid energy economic model has been applied to assess the electricity sector of a developing country Bangladesh under different economic growth and CO₂ emission restriction scenarios. It is observed that changes in economic growth and consumption rate might necessitate significant increase in energy and particularly electricity demand. Moreover, optimal electricity generation mix is also highly related with the interactions among different economic sub-sectors at a particular time point. Due to limited potential in a densely populated region and intermittency nature, renewable energy options do not come into the energy mix automatically. However, under carbon restricted conditions, a good contribution from solar PV and wind power is expected replacing natural gas and coal-based electricity generation. Moreover, nuclear power shows great potential due to its relatively lower construction cost in emerging economies and potential to ensure energy security and self-sufficiency. So far, renewable energy sources have been highly utilized for off-grid projects in Bangladesh due to absence of grid connected electricity. Once electricity reaches each and every corner of the country, grid connected solar power could definitely contribute in a large scale. Success of the first nuclear project and pilot wind power projects would also decide the future of these clean technologies in the region. In order to formulate proper energy

and electricity generation and expansion policies considering environmental protection further investigation is essential. However, current study ensures that nuclear and renewable energy sources could play a significant role in the future electricity generation mix of Bangladesh to ensure sustainable economic growth.

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